

Electrochemistry and spectral studies of dinuclear dihydroxo-bridged copper(II) complexes

Krishna Srivastava*, Ashish Kumar Srivastava and Jagdish Prasad

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : dr_krishna_s@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : The electrochemical behaviour of di- μ -hydroxo-bis(2,2'-bipyridine)dicopper(II) sulphate pentahydrate [(bipy)Cu(μ -OH)₂Cu(bipy)]SO₄·5H₂O (1) and di- μ -hydroxo-bis(1,10-phenanthroline)dicopper(II) sulphate pentahydrate [(phen)Cu(μ -OH)₂Cu(phen)]SO₄·5H₂O (2) in aqueous 0.1 M sodium sulphate at pH 7.5 was studied at a glassy carbon working electrode (GCE) using cyclic voltammetry. Both these complexes undergo a diffusion-controlled single-electron quasi-reversible redox process (Cu^{II}Cu^{II}/Cu^{II}Cu^I) in the potential range +1000 to -500 mV vs Ag/AgCl. The cathodic peak potential shifts negatively with increasing scan rate (ν) and peak current ratio (I_{pa}/I_{pc}) is less than 1.0, representing EC mechanism. It is important to note that the reduction potential (E_{pc}) is less negative for complex 2 than for complex 1, owing to the strong π -acceptor character of 1,10-phenanthroline over 2,2'-bipyridine. The electronic spectra of these complexes were also recorded in aqueous solution.

Keywords : Electrochemistry, cyclic voltammetry, dihydroxo-bridged dinuclear copper(II) complexes, bipyridine, phenanthroline.

Introduction

Nature has specially designed many dinuclear metalloprotein active sites with carboxylate and histidine rich ligand donors located in chemically different environments around the two metal centers, an asymmetry that may also involve the coordination numbers and the geometry of the metal centers. These two metal centers often found in close proximity (3–4 Å) and are bridged via oxo, dihydroxo, carboxylate or imidazolate groups, such as to allow electronic interaction, which in turn is manifested in the physical properties of the metalloenzymes and so in model complexes, such as redox potentials, optical and magnetic characteristics¹. Hydroxo-bridged binuclear copper(II) complexes have been found² to be catalytically active for oxidative coupling reactions. Copper complexes containing phenanthroline bases have received considerable current interests in the nucleic acids chemistry due to their various applications following the discovery of the “chemical nuclease” activity of 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) complex of copper(I) in presence of hydrogen peroxide and a reducing agent by Sigman and coworkers³.

The pair of irreversible reduction waves observed in the CV of the di- μ -hydroxo copper(II) complex of L¹ correspond to sequential one electron reductions of the dicopper centers⁴. [Cu₂(L-6,6)(OH)₂]²⁺ undergoes two distinct, irreversible one-electron reduction processes⁵ at notably negative potential values :

whereas the hydroxy complex [Cu₂(L-5,5)(OH)₂]²⁺ undergoes two closely spaced two electron steps at relatively low potential values, according to the overall process :

Reduction to metallic copper is evidenced by the appearance of anodic stripping peak present in the reverse scan.

The present work stems from our continued interest in defining and evaluating the electrochemical and spectral behaviour of dinuclear dihydroxo-bridged copper(II) complexes of diimines. In our earlier paper⁶, we reported

the electrochemical and spectral studies of binuclear monohydroxo-bridged copper(II) complexes. Very recently, we have also reported⁷ the extended X-ray absorption fine structure (EXAFS) studies of monohydroxo-bridged and dihydroxo-bridged copper(II) complexes using synchrotron radiations. In this paper, the electrochemistry and spectral studies of two distorted square pyramidal dinuclear dihydroxo-bridged copper(II) complexes viz. [(bipy)Cu(μ -OH)₂Cu(bipy)]SO₄·5H₂O (**1**) and [(phen)Cu(μ -OH)₂Cu(phen)]SO₄·5H₂O (**2**) (where bipy = 2,2'-bipyridine and phen = 1,10-phenanthroline) in aqueous 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ at pH 7.5 are described at a glassy carbon working electrode (GCE) using cyclic voltammetry (CV).

Results and discussion

Typical cyclic voltammograms of 1 mM aqueous solutions of complexes **1** and **2** containing 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ at pH 7.5 at a scan rate 100 mV s⁻¹ are displayed in Fig. 1 and the CV data for the complexes are given in Table 1. Complex **1**, displayed one electron redox couple in the potential region 1000 to -500 mV with $E^{0'}$ = -180 mV vs Ag/AgCl (E_{pc} = -275 mV, E_{pa} = -84 mV and ΔE_p = 190 mV) and is assigned to a quasi-reversible one electron transfer^{8,9}:

In addition to this, a second irreversible anodic peak (a') also appeared at $E_{pa'} = 125$ mV (Table 1 and Fig. 1(a)). The cyclic voltammogram for complex **2** also shows only one redox couple (Fig. 1(b)) with $E^{0'}$ = -113 mV vs Ag/AgCl (E_{pc} = -197, E_{pa} = -21 and ΔE_p = 184 mV). Controlled potential coulometry of complex **1** at -375 mV vs Ag/AgCl in aqueous 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ at pH 7.5 confirms the involvement of one electron per molecule in reduction process⁸. It should be noted that the number of electrons transferred, 'n' in the reduction process were calculated using the equation, $Q = nFC$, where Q is the charge in Coulombs; F is the Faraday constant and C is the number of moles of the complex. The plots of I_{pc} vs square root of the scan rate ($v^{1/2}$) for complexes **1** and **2** give straight lines passing through origin (Fig. 2), showing that the reduction process is diffusion-controlled⁸. The anodic to cathodic current ratio (I_{pa}/I_{pc}) is less than 1.0 for both the complexes, showing that the electrode process involves EC mechanism⁸.

It should be noted that the reduction peak potential (E_{pc}) for complex **2** is less negative than complex **1**, conceivably owing to the better π -acceptor character of phen over bipy⁹. It should be mentioned that the redox potentials of the complexes are affected by various factors¹⁰ such as type of ligands, nature of the donor atoms, geometry of the complex, electron density on the central metal ion, solvent etc.

Interestingly, the spin-allowed d-d band envelope of both the di- μ -hydroxo dicopper(II) complexes (**1** and **2**) occurs in the 600 nm range in their aqueous solutions at pH 7.5, consistent with distorted square pyramidal structures for the copper(II) centers^{10,11}, although the maximum ($\lambda_{max} = 619$ nm, $\epsilon = 140$ L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ for **1**) is still found at higher energy for the complex **1** with respect to the complex **2** ($\lambda_{max} = 634$ nm, $\epsilon = 110$ L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹). The dominant feature of the electronic spectra of these complexes is the presence of intense LMCT absorptions between 278 and 310 nm. The LMCT bands occur at higher energy for **2** than for **1**. It is clear that these absorptions are largely due to OH⁻ \rightarrow Cu^{II} LMCT transitions, since it is known that for copper(II)-hydroxo-bridged complexes LMCT bands occur in this range¹¹. It should be noted that no simple correlation between the crystal field parameter (λ_{max}) and the formal potential, $E^{0'}$ has been found for these complexes.

Experimental

The complexes [(bipy)Cu(μ -OH)₂Cu(bipy)]SO₄·5H₂O (**1**) and [(phen)Cu(μ -OH)₂Cu(phen)]SO₄·5H₂O (**2**) were prepared according to procedure described earlier¹² and their purity was checked by chemical analyses. All reagents used were of analytical grade. The aqueous solutions of the complexes under investigation were freshly prepared. It should be noted that complex **2** is less soluble in water and therefore its clear solution was obtained by filtration through gravimetric filter paper before recording the cyclic voltammograms. The experimental details have been given in our earlier paper⁶. Controlled Potential Electrolysis (CPE) was carried out for calculating the number of electrons transferred in the reduction process. Electrolysis was done in 1×10^{-3} M aqueous solutions of complex containing 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ in a Basi Bulk electrolysis cell consisting of Reticulated Carbon Working Electrode, coiled platinum auxiliary electrode dipped in a

Note

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of complexes 1; a and 2; b in aqueous 0.1 M sodium sulphate (pH 7.5) at a scan rate 100 mV s⁻¹.

Table 1. CV data for 1 mM dihydroxo-bridged copper(II) complexes containing 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ in aqueous medium at pH 7.5

Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)	E _{pc} (mV)	E _{pa} (mV)	E _{pa'} (mV)	*E ^{0r} (mV)	ΔE _p (mV)	I _{pa} /I _{pc}
[(bipy)Cu ₂ (μ-OH) ₂ (bipy)]SO ₄ ·5H ₂ O (1)						
25	-254	-84	104	-169.0	170	0.46
50	-262	-84	116	-173.0	178	0.37
100	-275	-84	125	-180.0	190	0.39
200	-293	-84	-	-186.0	214	0.37
300	-304	-84	-	-194.0	220	0.39
[(phen)Cu ₂ (μ-OH) ₂ (phen)]SO ₄ ·5H ₂ O (2)						
25	-173	-33	-	-113	160	0.81
50	-193	-27	-	-112	170	0.80
100	-197	-21	-	-113	184	0.88
200	-205	-13	-	-109	192	1.0
300	-205	-10	-	-107	195	0.97

$$*E^{0r} = 1/2 (E_{pa} + E_{pc})$$

Fig. 2. Plots of I_{pc} vs v^{1/2} for complexes 1 and 2.

separate cell containing 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ in aqueous solution only and Ag/AgCl as a reference electrode. Nitrogen gas was initially purged for 30 min with constant stirring

the solution and then N₂ was blanketed over the constantly stirred cell solution during the electrolysis. All the electrochemical experiments were performed at a constant temperature 25 ± 0.5 °C. Room temperature electronic absorption spectra of 1 mM aqueous solutions of **1** and **2** were measured in the range 1000–250 nm with a Perkin-Elmer UV-Visible spectrophotometer Model Lambda 35 available in our laboratory.

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